

Psocoptera

- p.1 Psocoptera unidentified
- p.2 Psocoptera_undet, Ecuador 03
- p.3 Psocoptera_FW articulation 02
- p.4 Psocoptera_venation 01

Psocoptera unidentified Taiwan

arculus present
 ↗
 ↘

arculus replaced by a fusion
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 ↘

Cu short, weak R & MA & MP & CuA completely fused

PSOCOPTERA: Ecuador Pichincha

Psocoptera

Ecuador, Pichincha, Tinalandia

FW Psocoptera wing articulation

San Francisco

PR-Cu long, separate from tergum
Note plesiomorphic arrangement of sclerites

Psocoptera venation: FSCA Gainesville, Florida

CuP either present or absent in claval line